

ISLAM IN THE WORKS OF CENTRAL ASIAN SCHOLARS STATEMENT OF ECONOMIC IDEAS IN THE TEACHING

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Annotation: In this article, one of the types of activities in the human society in the Kuran is relations in the field of economy and their importance, as well as the opinions of Central Asian sages about economic relations in their works.

Keywords: Kuran, human, economy, science, world, field, activity, parents, relationship, religion, relatives, law, culture.

Kuran is the activity of human society One of the types is relations in the field of economy. Because the main characteristics of people in economic relations appears. Kuran is a divine command to people It is based on the fact that all people on earth are children of one parent, Adam and Eve, and therefore brothers and sisters. For example, in the 13th verse of Surah "Hujurat", "O people, We created you from one father (Adam) and one mother (Mama Eve) and spread them across the earth in the form of various peoples, tribes and peoples, so that you may be one. - get to know each other and develop affection. Surely the most honorable of you in the sight of Allah is the most pious. Indeed, Allah is All-Knowing and All-Aware". In Islam, "taqwa" means to do righteous and good deeds and not to do evil, forbidden, and things that cause suffering to mankind. Therefore, piety is one of the main dimensions in determining the superiority of people over each other. This advantage is formed by recognizing the rights of others to live and marry with spiritual and spiritual education.

Separation of economic ideas in Kuran into several groups possible One of them is first of all honest labor, especially the farmer, The work of cattle breeders and artisans is glorified, they are encouraged to live their lives on the basis of honesty, and it is emphasized that work is the basis of all wealth. The second group of ideas is commercial, that is, the market in a broader sense special attention is paid to their relations. For example, in Surah An-Nisa (verse 29) "Do not spend your wealth unfairly (such as theft, robbery, usury, bribery, gambling) among yourselves! Maybe with mutual consent Make a fortune through trade", it is said. However, it is repeatedly emphasized that vices such as usury and bribery are haraam from the point of view of Shariah. The third group of economic ideas is related to property and inheritance issues directed. The sanctity of property, betrayal of someone's property (especially betrayal of trust) is condemned, even envying someone's property is considered a great sin.

There are also separate opinions about land ownership stated. For example, in verse 40 of Surah Moida, the earth is fertile it is emphasized that only things obtained by using it belong to a person. In Islam, the inequality of the society is recognized as the destiny from time immemorial. but honesty and correctness are ordered, lying, stealing, it is forbidden to earn income without work. Severe punishments are prescribed for making this mistake (Surah al-Maida, verse 38), “but whoever repents and corrects himself after such oppression, Allah will surely accept his repentance” (verse 39). Borrowing and giving, inheritance, it in Kuranof Allah Taala The ideas of distribution (Sura 4, verse 8), kindness to orphans and widows, and the types and amount of taxes are also of great importance. Betrayal of orphans is declared as one of the greatest sins. It is also said that mutual help is necessary, but not in bad deeds and enmity. In the deeper understanding of Islamic teachings, the next document after Kuranis the Hadith Sharifs of our Prophet Muhammad Alaihis Salam.

Here are some examples from Hadith Sharifs: There are three signs of hypocrisy: lying, breaking promises failure to withdraw and betrayal of deposit. It is forbidden for an emir to take a gift, and for a judge to take a bribe is an apostasy. Enter the houses of the rich less often, otherwise you will not appreciate the blessings that God has given you. Begging is allowed only in one of the following three categories:

1. To a person who pays for food;
2. To a heavy debtor;
3. To the poor poor person.[1]

Even when it is clear that the doomsday will happen when you have a seedling in your hand with the intention of making bread, plant it if you can. leave it Whoever is thrifty in life will never fall into poverty. Both the giver and the receiver are doomed to hell. Be like a shepherd in relation to science, but science don't just be a narrator. It should be emphasized that the Hadith Sharifs collected by al-Tirmidhi and al-Bukhari, among the Central Asian sages, are considered the most reliable in the Islamic world. The legal basis of economic relations is a component of Islamic jurisprudence. Our compatriot Marginani's work “Hidaya” is one of them. The full name of the great scientist Burkhaniddin al-Marginani is Ali Ibn Bakr Ibn Abdul Jalil al-Fargani arRishtani al-Marginani, he was born on September 23, 1123. He is known by the names of Burhoniddin Valmilla (Evidence of the Islamic Religion) and Burhoniddin al-Marginani due to the fact that he mastered the Kuran and Hadith sciences perfectly and had an in-depth knowledge of fiqh - Islamic jurisprudence and created incomparable masterpieces in this field. The scientist received his initial education in Margilon,

then moved to Samarkand, which was the religious and educational center of Movarunnahr at that time, and lived there until the end of his life. In the creation of their works, the works of the founders of the four sects of Sunnis in Islam learned About ten of his works have reached us. “Al-Hidaya” His work was written in Samarkand in 1178. This work has become the main guide on fiqh issues of the Hanafi school. Later, it became famous throughout the Muslim world and was recognized as the most accurate and consistent work on Muslim jurisprudence. Each of the sentences presented in the work consists of careful, concise and short words. The first book of “Al-Hidaya” consists of four volumes, each of which analyzes separate problems. This book was published in 1994 with a commentary by Professor A.Kh. Saidov. The content of the book is as follows:

1 - dedicated to worship issues of obligatory acts such as ablution, prayer, fasting, zakat and haj.

2 - covers issues such as family law, slave issues, partnerships and endowment property.

3 - sales, money problems, guarantees, duties of judges, testimony, returning from testimony given, authority, claim, confession, peace, partnering with money in one business, depositing money, lending money , gift, lease, slaves given limited freedom based on certain conditions, issues related to guardianship, coercion, patronage, invasion are covered;

4 - intercession, distribution of inheritance, farming and gardening It deals with issues such as contracts, sacrifices, bad things against Sharia, development of abandoned and protected lands, hunting, mortgages, crimes, alimony payments, and wills.[2]

It can be seen from the composition of the issues covered in this work that it is very embodies rich historical experience. Such people Humanity and justice are of great importance in the stability of relations between It is noted that it is especially necessary to observe the rules of justice, correctness, honesty, and humanity in commercial affairs. The sin of betraying someone’s rights and deceiving people is described as grave. Therefore, “Al-Hidaya” has been serving as one of the most reliable sources for the countries of the Islamic world for eight centuries. Fulfillment of Sharia rulings presented in the work is considered an important factor in the formation of high moral and human qualities. Sufism, that is, Sufism, is one of the important trends in the development of thought that appeared in accordance with Islamic principles. These teachings originated in the Arab world in the 8th-9th centuries and reached the land of Movaraunnahr in the 10th-11th centuries. This teaching promotes enlightenment, honesty and

justice, respect for universal values. The essence of Sufism is the fight against all the bad qualities of lust, lust, and wealth. Its purpose is to educate a perfect person. The Sufi doctrine of nafs refers to vices in human nature that tarnish his honor, including ignorance, arrogance, worldliness, bribery, theft, greed, greed, avarice, etc. . In order to overcome the ego, a person is tested, for this he needs to understand his identity. A person's identity consists of a mental and a physical identity. The spiritual self was created in the divine space and sent to this world for testing and purification. This spiritual self is tested through lust and purified through love. These two opposing forces are always fighting each other. The more a person is subject to his own desires, the more he moves away from goodness, becomes spiritually polluted, and he himself is brought down. Representatives of this doctrine include Ahmed Yassavi, Sulayman Bakirgani, Najmuddin Kubro and Bahauddin Naqshbandlar are included. Today, their rich heritage serves a great purpose in fully understanding the concepts of homeland, nation and perfect human being. Burkhaniddin Al-Marginani. With the honor of independence, the rich spiritual heritage of scholars was returned to the people. Abul Hasan Ali ibn Abu Bakr ibn Abdujamil, who laid the foundations of Islamic law with his immortal works, was born in the village of Rishtan of Fergana province, and he lived and worked in the years 511-593 AH (1115-1197 AD). The future scientist received his first education in Rishton, Margilon, and later in Samarkand, He increased his knowledge in the big cities of Bukhara and Movarunnahr. He created unique works on fiqh such as "Bidayat al-mubtait", "Nashr al-Mashad", "Kitab at-tajnis", "Almadad". His most famous work is "Hidaya fi furi' alfiqh" ("Guide to the fields of jurisprudence"). This work is considered to be a widely used Sharia manual, that is, a code of Sunnism in the Hanafi school of Islam.[3]

In the field of jurisprudence, there was a movement to write books before. 1048 Abul Hasan al-Kuduri, who died in "Hidaya" in the countries where the Hanafi school was spread in his time, especially among the Muslims of Central Asia, the North Caucasus and the Volga region, it gained fame as the main guide. This work consists of 4 volumes and 56 chapters. Based on the verses of the Holy Kuran, the author's opinions and conclusions on Sharia issues are given. All names of imams of the Hanafi sect, as well as opinions of representatives of other sects, are widely interpreted in the work. The book describes in detail the names related to family-marriage issues (marriage, divorce), the legal rules and punishments related to their implementation are defined. Social-economic and legal issues from the Islamic point of view: property and financial relations, especially inheritance, ways of dividing it, crime and punishment, civil rights are

also shown. Also, a number of issues specific to Islam, in particular, taking loot and its distribution, some persecutions and permissiveness in life activities are mentioned. Burkhaniddin al-Marginani was an extremely knowledgeable person, a righteous jurist, and one of the sages of hadith science. He knew the Kuran by heart, was able to interpret it, was a poet, a writer. It is recorded in historical manuscripts that the ancestors of scholars were also people who knew Muslim law well. The work "Hidaya" includes all aspects of Muslim law and is considered to be an extremely wide source of research. In the work, special attention is paid to the issue of zakat, a special chapter is devoted to it. The opinions expressed regarding payments from livestock and personal property are very important. The writing style of the work is such that, along with well-known issues, rare cases, subtle aspects of this or that issue are explained in detail. To put it in the language of the present time, it looks like a complete commentary on the issued basic law. The book contains interesting information about who should pay zakat and how much. Usually, zakat must be paid at the expense of one fortieth part (2.5 percent) of the income. In animal husbandry, one out of 40 goats is given as zakat, if the number of animals is small, it is not taken. Lambs under one year old are not included in the payment of zakat. In the case of horses, the calculation is different, that is, zakat must be paid in the amount of one dinar or 9 percent of the horse's value. But donkeys, mules and other working animals (ox, camel) are not charged. If they are traded, the situation will change and zakat will be given. Goats, calves and calves under the age of one year are not included in the general account, but one out of 25 camels, two camels from 66, and three camels from more than 145 must be given as zakat. There is an important point here that it is said that if the owner of the property can pay zakat in the form of money instead of the property (in kind), equal to its value.[4]

Another important instruction is worth noting that the collector of zakat is the most it is required that he buys not a good (good) product, but an average price product. In addition, it is indicated that zakat can be paid in advance. Average nisab (tax) on zakat from silver items amount that can be taken) is set at 200 dirhams, 2.5 percent (ie 5 dirhams) of zakat is charged. If the amount of silver is more than 200 dirhams, zakat is given for each additional 40 dirhams and so on. The amount of zakat on gold is unique. Zakat is not taken up to 20 misqals (one misqal is 4.5 grams on average), half a misqal (2.5%) is paid from 20 misqals. In excess of 20 misqals, 2 carats of every 4 misqals, (i.e. 1 out of 12 ounces) must be given as zakat. Personal, private property settlement is determined by silver or equivalent. Even silver and gold are based on a common valuation can be

reduced to a single value. One-fifth (20 percent) of zakat must be collected for the found mine treasure. For example, this method is used when a treasure is found somewhere or in a cultivated area. Zakat is not paid on precious stones, because stones are exempt from zakat. One tenth (10 percent) of the harvest on lands irrigated naturally (with rain and snow water) is taken as a tithe. However, forests, pastures, and fields are exempted from zakat. Half of the tithe (50 percent) is taxed at the expense of artificially irrigated lands.[5]

Burkhaniddin al-Marginani also describes the rules of distribution of zakat in his work. Valuable opinions were expressed about the possibility of using the collected zakat by representatives of certain categories of the population: the poor, the needy, zakat collectors, and debtors. We think that this work of our grandfather is extremely rich and as a valuable resource, it should be taught in higher education institutions. Currently, there is a Russian translation of this work. The first and remaining volumes of the work should be translated into Uzbek. There is no doubt that it will serve as a priceless treasure in awakening the feelings of honesty and religion, justice and truth in the hearts of our youth.

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